

**University Libraries in Kalyan Karnataka Region:
Trends in ICT Facilities and services**

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ABSTRACT

Research has shown that information technology has a tremendous effect on higher educational institutions particularly universities and in this direction efforts are made to determine the extent of impact of technology on universities in Kalyan Karnataka region and results are discussed.

Keywords: Information Technology, Electronic Resources, Universities in Kalyan Karnataka (Hyderabad Karnataka), User Research

INTRODUCTION

In recent years the technology has made pervasive change in teaching and learning methodologies. Information technology now plays an important role in improving the library facilities. On the other side, due to declining budget (Mahajan, 2005) and the rising costs of journals, many Indian universities and college libraries cannot afford to subscribe to all the required journals and online databases which have led to the significance of National Consortia like e-shodhsindhu consortia resources. This has provided a great source to access electronic information resources on the net and this call for effective ICT infrastructure, awareness and optimization of electronic resources to serve the very purpose. Such switch from print collections to digital collections has an impact on library users and user's perception of the library. Therefore it is worth to study to assess the impact of information technology on university library services and its users in Kalyan Karnataka region.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are to determine

- Availability of ICT infrastructure and use of technological devices in academic and research activities
- Use of ICT facilities and e-resources in libraries
- Impact of ICT resources on research and academic activities
- Results of association between different variables with respect to Use and impact of ICT services in the University Libraries of Kalyan Karnataka Region:

METHODOLOGY

For the present study the Karnataka Hyderabad region is considered as a geographical region of the study. The four universities have selected on the basis of lottery method. The details are shown as under:

Table 1: Universities of the respondents

University	Frequency	Percentage
Central University of Karnataka, Kadaganchi	390	46.5
Gulbarga University, Kalaburgi	226	27.0
University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur	66	7.90
Karnataka Veterinary Animal & Fisheries Sciences University, Bidar	156	18.6
Total	838	100.0

It is found from the table that out of 838 respondents, a majority proportion of the respondents, less than two-fourth (390, 46.5%), is from Central University of Karnataka. A significant proportion of the respondents, more than one-fourth, (226, 27%), is from Gulbarga University. A small proportion of the respondents, less than one-fifth, (156, 18.6%) is from University of Agricultural Sciences; and a very small proportion of the

respondents, less than one-tenth, (66, 7.9%) is from Karnataka Veterinary Animal & Fisheries University.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Discipline of the respondents

Discipline	Frequency	Percentage
Social Science	240	28.6
Humanities	78	09.3
Pure Sciences	376	44.9
Management	72	08.6
Engineering & allied	72	08.6
Total	838	100.0

The table 2 shows that the disciplines of the respondents which they belong. It may be seen from the above table that out of 838 respondents, a majority proportion of the respondents, more than two-fifth (376, 44.9%), is from pure science discipline. A significant proportion of the respondents, more than one-fourth, (240, 28.6%), is from social science. A small proportions of the respondents, less than one-tenth, (78, 9.3%), (72, 8.6%) and (72, 8.6%) is from humanities, management and engineering and allied disciplines respectively.

- **ICT infrastructure and use of technological devises in academic and research activities**

Use of ICT infrastructure and devises by the research participants for their academic and research activities are explored. It is found that majority of the research participants (760, 90.7%) always used personal computers. It is found that majority of them never used interactive whiteboards (287, 34.2%) and learning management systems (223, 26.6%). It is also found that majority of them never used video conferencing systems (352, 42%) but majority of them (387, 46.2%) always used mobile/ smart phones. They often used projection system (338, 40.3%).

As far as the access to the technological equipments in their respective libraries is concerned; it is found that majority of the research participants always (460, 54.39%) had access to personal computers/ laptops. It is found that majority of them never (302, 36%) had access to interactive whiteboards, learning management systems/ VLE (WebCT, Moodle etc.) (376, 44.9%), and video conferencing systems (321, 38.3%) but it is found that majority of them always (388, 46.3%) had used mobile/ smart phones and LCD projector system (389, 46.4%) in their respective libraries.

- **Use of ICT facilities and e-resources in libraries**

Majority of the research participants have opined that they use their libraries weekly (486, 58%) and majority of them (686, 81.9%) have access to Internet facility in their respective libraries.

As far as the access to the e-resources availability in their library is concerned; it is found that majority of them have no (675, 80.5%), (712, 85%), (678, 80.9%), (513, 61.2%), (609, 72.7%), (445, 53.1%), (464, 55.4%), (683, 81.5%), (685, 81.7%), (732, 87.4%), (447, 53.3%), (572, 68.3%), (435, 51.9%), (706, 84.2%), (688, 82.1%) and (601, 71.7%) access to e-resource of American Chemical Society, American Institute of Physics, American Physical Society, Annual Reviews, Blackwell Publishing, Emerald (LIS collection), Encyclopaedia Britannica, Institute of Physics Publishing, Institute for studies in industrial development, JCCC, JSTOR, Nature, Oxford University Press, Portland Press, Project Muse and Royal Society of Chemistry respectively.

According to the research participants, the access to the e-resources in their respective libraries; the majority of them opined they have (431, 51.4%), (473, 56.4%), (502, 59.9%), (559, 66.7%) and (588, 70.2%) access to e-resources of Cambridge University Press, Elsevier, Science Direct, Taylor & Francis and Springer link respectively.

- **Impact of ICT resources on research and academic activities**

This section has explored the extent of impact of ICT resources has made on the research participant's research and academic activities. It is found that the ICT resource – library websites had greater impact (376, 44.9%) on them. Full text databases had medium impact (360, 43%) on them. E-journals and e-books had greater impact (477, 56.9%) and (462, 55.1%) on the participants respectively these results are at par with the studies conducted by Dhukate and Bhoite (2015), Saravanan and Nagadeepa (2016) and Singh (2017). Online catalogue had also greater impact (323, 38.5%) on them. It is found that online reference works had greater impact (409, 48.8%) on them. Internet/ email and Websites/ homepages also had greater impact (587, 70%) and (460, 54.9%) on them respectively, a review study of Bindu (2016) also emphasized this.

As far as the extent of impact that ICT resource- blogs/ portals is concerned; it had medium impact (391, 46.7%) on the research participants. It has found that the CD-ROM databases had not much impact (440, 52.5%) on research participants.

However, to increase the use of ICT technologies universities have organizing training programs and majority of the research participants opined positively (652, 77.8%) that their respective universities are conducting training programmes to promote e-resources/ICT technologies.

To integrate ICT technologies into research, teaching and learning activities, the perceptions about the extent of importance for given suggestions have explored. It is found that the suggestion – better access to technological equipments, technological hands-on training/ courses, training/ courses in pedagogical use of ICT, reliability of equipment, time to prepare, explore and develop and availability of high quality equipment has perceived very important (554, 66.1%), (488, 58.2%), (368, 43.9%), (454, 54.2%), (495, 59.1%) and (538, 64.2%) by research participants respectively.

It is found that the suggestion related to the developing policies on using ICT across curriculum, majority of the research participants opined that it is important to some extent (484, 57.8%) to integrate ICT technology into teaching, research and learning activities.

• Results of association

To explore the associations between different variables the chi-square test has applied. Here the designation has considered as independent variable and other responses related to the use of technological devices as dependent variable. It is found that almost all the responses to use of technological devices i.e. personal computers, interactive whiteboards, learning management systems, mobile phones and projection systems have found significant association with designation of the respondents with 0.05 level of significance. Only response to video conferencing systems have not found associated with the designation of the respondents.

As far as the perceptions of the respondents about extent quality support of ICT in their learning, teaching and research activities are concerned; the significant associations are found between communicating and or networking and organizing work and keeping records with 0.05 level of significance but it has not found between own development and learning and help for preparing lessons/ accessing and learning e-resources with designation of the respondents.

While exploring level of acquaintance in using ICT software's among respondents, almost all the variables i.e. familiarity in using Windows, Windows NT, MS-Word, MS-Excel, MS-

Power point, MS-Front Page, MS-Access, C/C++, Java scripts, HTML/DHTML and SPSS found associated with the designation of the respondents with 0.05 level of significance. Only use of Linux software not found association with the designation of the respondents.

Frequency of visiting library has also found associated with respondents designation with 0.05 level of significance.

While exploring access of e-resources available in respondent's respective libraries; it is found that access to various e-resources by vivid sources i.e. American Chemical Society, American Institute of Physics, Annual Reviews, Emerald (LIS collection), Institute of Physics Publishing, Institute of studies in industrial development, JCCC, Nature, Oxford University Press, Portland Press, Royal Society of Chemistry, Science Direct, Springer link and Taylor & Francis and respondents designation with 0.05 level of significance. While it has not found with the e-resources by Blackwell Publishing, Cambridge University Press, Elsevier, Encyclopaedia Britannica, JSTOR and Project Muse.

Use of e-resources and services over last five years found association with designation of the respondents with 0.05 level of significance.

However, extent of impact of ICT on respondents research and academic activities is concerned; it is found that e-resource i.e. full text databases, e-books, Websites/ homepages, blogs/ portals and CD-ROM databases found associated with designation of the respondents with 0.05 level of significance, while other e-resources i.e. library websites, e-journals, online catalogue, online reference works, Internet/ email are found not associated with designation of the respondents.

As far as the perceived importance of suggestions made to integrate technology into teaching, research and learning activities are concerned; it is found that all suggestions i.e. better access to technological equipments, technological hands-on training/ course, training course in pedagogical use of ICT, policies on using ICT across curriculum, reliability of equipment, time to prepare, explore and develop and availability of high quality equipment found associated with the designation of the respondents with 0.05 level of significance.

CONCLUSION

It can also be concluded that people have access to IT facilities in their respective libraries but many important journals and e-resources are out of their reach. E-resources i.e. e-journals, e-books, database, reference work had greater impact on research and academic activities of universities but though universities conducting ICT programs for users but the scale is found limited. To integrate ICT in teaching, research and learning activities the

access to better equipments, hands-on training, and courses in pedagogical use of ICT are felt more important.

Based on the study findings and discussion, it is recommended that Advanced computer laboratories and other adequate infrastructure should be developed by universities. Interdisciplinary research studies should be taken to explore the interconnections between behavioural and other factors with their dynamic mobility. Training programmes, hands on experiences, training courses on ICT should be ongoing part of university library functioning and should be included into the curriculum of each stream. Innovative computer software's and programs and other ICT tools must be developed or devised for students to develop their interest in their creative, critical and research thinking and there is a need to promote policies which will make universities to advance and upgrade their existing infrastructure.

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